

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Towards decoding selective attention through cochlear implant electrodes as sensors in subjects with contralateral acoustic hearing

To cite this article: Nina Aldag *et al* 2022 *J. Neural Eng.* **19** 016023

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [EEG-based auditory attention detection: boundary conditions for background noise and speaker positions](#)
Neetha Das, Alexander Bertrand and Tom Francart
- [Review of real brain-controlled wheelchairs](#)
Á Fernández-Rodríguez, F Velasco-Álvarez and R Ron-Angevin
- [Epidural recordings in cochlear implant users](#)
S Haumann, G Bauernfeind, M J Teschner *et al.*

The Breath Biopsy® Guide
Fourth edition

FREE

DOWNLOAD THE FREE E-BOOK

BREATH BIOPSY

OWLSTONE MEDICAL

PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED
27 August 2021REVISED
21 December 2021ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
21 January 2022PUBLISHED
10 February 2022

Original content from
this work may be used
under the terms of the
[Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 licence](#).

Any further distribution
of this work must
maintain attribution to
the author(s) and the title
of the work, journal
citation and DOI.

Towards decoding selective attention through cochlear implant electrodes as sensors in subjects with contralateral acoustic hearing

Nina Aldag , Andreas Büchner, Thomas Lenarz and Waldo Nogueira*

Department of Otolaryngology, Hannover Medical School and Cluster of Excellence 'Hearing4all', Hanover, Germany

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: Nogueira.Vazquez.Waldo@mh-hannover.de**Keywords:** selective attention, cochlear implant, cortical auditory evoked potentials, electroencephalography, neural tracking, intracochlear electrodes, backward telemetry

Abstract

Objectives. Focusing attention on one speaker in a situation with multiple background speakers or noise is referred to as auditory selective attention. Decoding selective attention is an interesting line of research with respect to future brain-guided hearing aids or cochlear implants (CIs) that are designed to adaptively adjust sound processing through cortical feedback loops. This study investigates the feasibility of using the electrodes and backward telemetry of a CI to record electroencephalography (EEG). **Approach.** The study population included six normal-hearing (NH) listeners and five CI users with contralateral acoustic hearing. Cortical auditory evoked potentials (CAEP) and selective attention were recorded using a state-of-the-art high-density scalp EEG and, in the case of CI users, also using two CI electrodes as sensors in combination with the backward telemetry system of these devices, denoted as implant-based EEG (iEEG). **Main results.** In the selective attention paradigm with multi-channel scalp EEG the mean decoding accuracy across subjects was 94.8% and 94.6% for NH listeners and CI users, respectively. With single-channel scalp EEG the accuracy dropped but was above chance level in 8–9 out of 11 subjects, depending on the electrode montage. With the single-channel iEEG, the selective attention decoding accuracy could only be analyzed in two out of five CI users due to a loss of data in the other three subjects. In these two CI users, the selective attention decoding accuracy was above chance level. **Significance.** This study shows that single-channel EEG is suitable for auditory selective attention decoding, even though it reduces the decoding quality compared to a multi-channel approach. CI-based iEEG can be used for the purpose of recording CAEPs and decoding selective attention. However, the study also points out the need for further technical development for the CI backward telemetry regarding long-term recordings and the optimal sensor positions.

1. Introduction

The cochlear implant (CI) is a neuroprosthesis that is used to rehabilitate severe to profound sensorineural hearing loss. The CI stimulates the auditory nerve electrically and thereby mimics the bottom-up function of the peripheral auditory system. Most CI users obtain good speech recognition in quiet. However, CI users face difficulties to understand speech in the so-called 'cocktail-party' scenario (Cherry 1953), where speech is presented in the presence of simultaneous

disturbing sounds (e.g. Bronkhorst 2000, Zeng *et al* 2008).

The ability to focus on a conversation in a noisy 'cocktail party' scenario is related to auditory selective attention. The underlying neural mechanisms involved in selective attention are still a topic of current research. The selective attention processes include the enhancement of an attended 'auditory object' (e.g. Alain and Arnott 2000) and the suppression of unattended objects by making use of the 'bottom-up' and 'top-down' mechanisms of

the auditory pathway (e.g. Kaya and Elhilali 2017). Normal-hearing (NH) listeners can use these mechanisms to selectively attend to one speaker (e.g. Mesgarani and Chang 2012). CI users, on the other hand, have difficulties with this task, since CIs are designed to mimic the bottom-up auditory pathway and not the top-down neural feedback loop. The idea of decoding selective attention is to reproduce neural selective attention mechanisms through the measurement of neural signals and subsequent signal processing. For this purpose, neural signals are measured through electroencephalography (EEG) or magnetoencephalography and filtered in order to reconstruct the attended speech or to decode the locus of attention from the neural signals (e.g. Ding and Simon 2014, O'Sullivan *et al* 2015). The technology may find application in closed-loop CI or hearing aid systems, e.g. for neurally-steered hearing prostheses that can identify the attended speech to steer speech enhancement algorithms (e.g. O'Sullivan *et al* 2017). Other applications can be found in the objective fitting of CIs or in the clinical evaluation of hearing development in children or disabled CI users (e.g. McLaughlin *et al* 2013, Finke *et al* 2017).

The feasibility of decoding selective attention from single-trial EEG has been shown in various previous studies in NH listeners (e.g. Mirkovic *et al* 2015, O'Sullivan *et al* 2015) and CI users (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b, Paul *et al* 2020). The use of scalp EEG, however, is not applicable in the clinical routine or in everyday applications. Around-the-ear-EEG, as used by Bleichner *et al* (2016) and Mirkovic *et al* (2016) in NH listeners and by Nogueira *et al* (2019b) in CI users, and in-ear-EEG, as used by Fiedler *et al* (2017) in NH listeners, is one possibility to reduce the visibility and to maximize the portability of the recording system. However, non-invasive recordings from the scalp can contain a lot of artifacts, caused by electrode displacement, body motion, ocular and muscle movement (Islam *et al* 2016). The quality of invasive EEG is often better because invasive EEG is less prone to ocular artifacts (Ball *et al* 2009), filter effects of the tissue and spatial distortions from the skull (Waldert 2016).

Modern CIs are equipped with backward telemetry capabilities that can be used to record voltage fluctuations around the electrode contacts. The idea of this work was to use electrodes of a CI in combination with the CI backward telemetry system to record neural signals and to decode selective attention from these CI-based recordings. The CI backward telemetry systems are primarily used for impedance measurement, electrocochleography (ECochG) and the recording of electrically evoked compound action potentials (ECAPs). ECochG can be used to actively monitor cochlear responses during the electrode insertion to assist in predicting electrode location

and preventing intraoperative trauma (e.g. Calloway *et al* 2014, Acharya *et al* 2016, Harris *et al* 2017), to estimate residual hearing objectively (e.g. Koka *et al* 2017) or to characterize electric and acoustic interaction (e.g. Imsiecke *et al* 2020, Krüger *et al* 2020). The recording of ECAPs is an established method to assess the CI function and the auditory nerve function intra- and postoperatively (e.g. Christov *et al* 2016) and may assist in the fitting of CIs (e.g. Botros and Psarros 2010, McKay *et al* 2013, McKay and Smale 2017). ECAPs and ECochG have been successfully transferred into clinical applications. Similarly, the advantages of recording EEG with invasive CI electrodes would be the easy applicability in CI users and the proximity between the electrodes and the auditory cortex. However, most of the currently available CI backward telemetry is limited by the short measurement windows due to hardware restrictions. McLaughlin *et al* (2012) used the telemetry system of CIs from the company Cochlear Ltd to measure early AEPs, also known as the auditory brainstem responses, and late AEPs, also known as cortical auditory evoked potentials (CAEPs). Recording of CAEPs, which normally requires continuous recording of up to 1 s, was realized by a combination of repeated measurements with shifting time windows. This procedure was highly time consuming and thus is not practically applicable in clinical routine measurements. Somers *et al* (2021) performed continuous EEG recording via a CI from the company Cochlear Ltd using a percutaneous connector. Moreover, a high-quality external amplifier was used and the invasive CI electrodes was combined with non-invasive scalp channels for a hybrid EEG recording. However, Somers *et al* (2021) approach also lacks the practical applicability because it requires an invasive procedure which goes hand in hand with an increase of multiple risks for the patient, such as infection. Nevertheless, both approaches prove the general feasibility of CI-based recording of cortical signals such as CAEPs and motivate the development of fully implantable CI-based EEG (iEEG).

In the current study, the iEEG was based on the electrodes and the backward telemetry system of Advanced Bionics CIs. With the current system it is not possible to record and to stimulate simultaneously. For this reason, the study population included CI users with contralateral acoustic hearing, so that it was possible to record cortical signals on the CI side while presenting the stimuli to the acoustically hearing ear. This study population will be referred to as CI users along this manuscript. First, CAEPs were measured to investigate the general feasibility of recording cortical potentials with the CI. Another restriction of the current system was that only a single recording channel was utilizable. For this reason, it was investigated if selective

Table 1. Demographics of NH listeners. The stimulation order refers to the order in which the stimuli voices were presented. F = female; M = male.

ID	Gender	Age	Acoustic stimulation side	Stimulation order
NH1	F	24	Left	F–M
NH2	M	27	Right	F–M
NH3	M	31	Left	M–F
NH4	M	27	Right	F–M
NH5	M	35	Right	M–F
NH6	M	37	Left	F–M

Table 2. Demographics of CI users with contralateral acoustic hearing. The stimulation order refers to the order in which the stimuli voices were presented. F = female; M = male.

ID	Gender	Age	Implant	Electrode	Acoustic stimulation side	Stimulation order
CI1	M	73	Ultra 3D	Mid-Scala	Left	M–F
CI2	M	73	HiRes90K Advantage	Mid-Scala	Right	F–M
CI3	M	53	Ultra	Mid-Scala	Left	M–F
CI4	M	80	Ultra	Mid-Scala	Left	F–M
CI5	F	49	Ultra 3D	SlimJ	Left	M–F

attention decoding was possible from single-channel recordings and with monaural stimulus presentation. Those single-channel scalp EEG recordings were compared to the single-channel iEEG using a selective attention paradigm. The results of these experiments offer insights into the current restrictions and possibilities and might promote further optimization of CI-based recording systems.

2. Methods

2.1. Subjects

Five CI users with contralateral acoustic hearing (four male, one female; mean age: 66 years) and six NH listeners (five male, one female; mean age: 33 years) participated in the study. All subjects were native German speakers and reported no history of neurological disorders. The demographics of NH listeners and CI users and their measurement conditions are provided in tables 1 and 2, respectively. Please note that NH subjects and CI subjects are not age-matched and have a different degree of hearing loss.

The CI users were unilaterally implanted with an Advanced Bionics device with a fully inserted electrode array. All CI users had residual acoustic hearing on the contralateral ear to the CI. The audiograms, measured on the acoustically hearing ear only, are provided in figure 1. Subject CI1, CI3 and CI4 wore a hearing aid on the acoustically hearing ear in daily life. The NH listeners served as a control group. All NH listeners had age-appropriate hearing with a hearing loss equal to or lower than 10 dB hearing level in the frequency range from 0.25–8 kHz. The stimulation side for NH subjects was chosen randomly.

2.2. Experimental setup

The experimental setup is shown in figure 2. The current study extended the experimental setup from

Nogueira *et al* (2019a, 2019b) to record iEEG through the backward telemetry and the electrodes of a CI.

Subjects were sitting in an electromagnetically and acoustically shielded chamber. The software Presentation version 20.1 (Neurobehavioral Systems, Inc., Berkeley, California) was used to present acoustic stimuli and visual input via a screen. Acoustic stimuli were presented via an amplification system (A-10, Pioneer Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) and inserted earphones (E-A-RTONE Gold 3 A, 3 M, St. Paul, Minneapolis).

The scalp EEG system consisted of an intracerebral electrode cap (Easycap GmbH, Herrschingen, Germany) and a BrainAmp amplification system (Brain Products GmbH, Gilchingen, Germany). The electrode cap comprised 96 passive sintered silver/silver chloride electrodes. A reference electrode was placed on the nose tip and a ground electrode on the forehead anterior to the midline frontal electrode (Fz). Recordings were performed with a sampling frequency of 1 kHz and an online filter from 0.2 to 250 Hz. The data was stored by Lab Recorder (Neurobehavioral Systems, Inc., Berkeley, California) in an extensible data format (.xdf). Apart from the multi-channel EEG (figure 3(a)) we also analyzed two different single-channel scalp EEG configurations (figure 3(b)). The first configuration was the vertex electrode (Cz) re-referenced against the mastoid electrode (Cz—mastoid). This configuration was expected to yield most promising selective attention decoding and CAEP results (e.g. Crosse *et al* 2016). A second single-channel EEG configuration was the CP5 or CP6 electrode behind the ear re-referenced to the mastoid electrode ('CI-like'). This configuration was supposed to mimic the CI electrode configuration as in Mao *et al* (2019). For single-channel recording we always used the electrodes

Figure 1. Audiograms of CI users on the acoustically hearing ear contralateral to the CI.

Figure 2. Experimental setup: the subject was sitting in an electromagnetically and acoustically shielded chamber. Acoustic stimuli were presented via in-ear phones in the contralateral ear to the CI or to one NH ear and optical input was provided via a screen. The scalp EEG recording (green) was synchronized through event markers in lab streaming layer between personal computer 2 and 3 (PC2, PC3). The recording via CI (orange) was captured by PC1 and synchronized through transistor–transistor logic (TTL) triggering between the trigger dongle and PC2. For NH subjects the setup was the same, except that PC1, the trigger dongle and the CPI-3 as well as the TTL components (all marked with orange color) were not used. BEDCS = bionic ear data collection system; CPI = clinical programming interface; LSL = lab streaming layer.

contralateral to the ear that was presented with the stimulus.

For the iEEG the subject's individual internal unit of the CI was connected to an external unit through a coil and a Naida Q90 sound processor. A custom made trigger dongle and a clinical programming interface (CPI 3; Advanced Bionics AG, Stäfa, Switzerland) connected the CI via USB to the research interface BEDCS app version 3.1 (Advanced Bionics AG, Stäfa, Switzerland), implemented in Matlab 2019b (The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, Massachusetts). The iEEG recording is a continuous data stream that is recorded through the backward telemetry of the CI.

In general, signals are recorded from the CI electrodes, amplified through an internal recording circuitry that is located in the implant and then transmitted through the radio-frequency link to the outer hardware. Details about this technology are published by Mens (2007). The configurations of the internal recording circuitry, which were designed for recording shorter signals like eCAPs, are not yet optimized for measuring continuous signals. This caused a drift in the signal that led to a saturation of the iEEG signal in some subjects. The data was stored in a Matlab file format (.mat). The equipment for the iEEG was provided by Advanced Bionics LLC (Valencia,

United States). The iEEG recordings were performed with a sampling frequency of 5625 Hz. Single-channel recordings were performed between the most apical intracochlear electrode (E0) as the active input and an extracochlear electrode, located on the implant case, as the reference input (figure 3(c)).

2.3. Stimuli

CAEPs were evoked through linearly-ramped 1 kHz sine tone burst stimuli. The rise and fall time of the ramp was 10 ms and the plateau time was 30 ms. The stimuli were presented 100 times with a repetition rate of ~ 1 Hz (the exact repetition rate depended on the processing speed of PC1). The measurement was conducted with three different loudness levels. The subject's individual loudness was adjusted through a ten-point loudness-rating scale (with 1 equivalent to 'extremely soft' and 10 equivalent to 'extremely loud'). The first level was defined as 7 ('loud but comfortable') and the second level as 3 ('soft'). The third level was without stimulus presentation and served as a baseline recording to characterize the noise floor.

The current study used the same selective attention paradigm as in Nogueira *et al* (2019a, 2019b). Two German stories, 'A drama in the air' by Jules Verne and 'The two brothers' by the Grimm Brothers, were presented to the subject. 'A drama in the air' was narrated by a male speaker, 'The two brothers' was narrated by a female speaker. In contrast to the two previous studies, the two stories were digitally combined and presented through one acoustic ear. For all CI users that wore a hearing device on the other ear, the stories were pre-processed digitally to amplify the sounds based on their individual audiogram. This was done by applying the 'half-gain rule', introduced by Lybarger (1944) which amplifies an audio signal at each frequency by half the hearing loss in dB.

The implementation of the 'half-gain rule' has been successfully used in the past (e.g. Krüger *et al* 2021). After this amplification the loudness was adjusted by the subject to reach level 6 ('comfortable') using the ten-point loudness-rating described above.

The stories were 24 min long and were divided into three sections of 8 min. Every section was divided into four subblocks of 2 min. After each section, the subject was able to take a break. The stories were presented twice, with the subject attending to one story the first time and to the other story the second time. At the start of each subblock, the subject was instructed to attend to a particular voice. The order of the to-be-attended stories was randomized across subjects (see tables 1 and 2 for details). Altogether, the procedure included 48 min recording time for each subject, excluding the time for breaks.

2.4. Behavioral response

In the selective attention experiment the subject was asked to answer questions about the attended story after each subblock to make sure that the correct story was attended. Four single-choice questions with four possible answers were displayed on the screen. The questions were answered with the numbers 1–4 on a keyboard. The purpose of these questions was to force the subject's attention to the correct story and to evaluate if the subjects were able to perform this task.

At the end of each story the subject was asked three questions about the difficulty of the task: 'How difficult was the task in general?', 'How easily could you focus on the story?' and 'How much did the other story distract you?'. The answers were rated from 1–4, with 1 equivalent to 'very easy' or 'not at all' and 4 equivalent to 'very difficult' or 'very much'. The purpose of this subjective evaluation was to reveal if any subject had major problems to perform the task.

2.5. Test procedure

A pure-tone audiogram was measured to determine the hearing status of the acoustic ear (CI users) and to validate NH status in the reference group. The subject's hair was washed and dried and the EEG cap was mounted onto the subjects head. The impedances of the scalp EEG electrodes were maintained below 20 k Ω by cleaning the skin with ethanol and applying an abrasive and conductive electrolyte gel (AbraLyt 2000; EasyCap GmbH, Herrschingen, Germany). CAEPs and selective attention measurements were recorded. During both measurements, the subject was asked to sit calm and relaxed in the measurement chamber, to keep the eyes open and to keep the visual focus on a white fixation cross on the black screen in front of the subject. Regular breaks were provided according to the needs of the subject. All sources of electromagnetic interference were removed from the chamber and the light was dimmed.

2.6. Data analysis

2.6.1. Pre-processing

Pre-processing of EEG data was performed offline in Matlab 2020a (The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, Massachusetts) using the EEGLAB toolbox (v2020.0; Delorme and Makeig 2004). The constant time delays of the EEG systems were compensated, i.e. the EEG had a delay of 77 ms with respect to the acoustic stimulation (Nogueira *et al* 2019b) and the iEEG started 250 ms before the acoustic stimulus was presented. A drift in iEEG data was removed by subtracting the low-pass filtered signal from the original recording. The low-pass filter was based on a moving average filter with a window width of 200 ms.

CAEPs recorded with iEEG and with EEG were filtered with a 4th order Butterworth bandpass filter from 1 to 20 Hz, using the `filtfilt`-function in Matlab for zero-phase filtering, and downsampled to 500 Hz. The data were epoched in 100 trials. The first five trials were excluded and the mean of all other trials was calculated. Significant peaks were identified using bootstrapping with 200 replicates.

Selective attention iEEG and EEG data was pre-processed according to the procedure of Nogueira *et al* (2019a, 2019b). EEG and iEEG were filtered using a 4th order Butterworth bandpass filter from 2–8 Hz, using the `filtfilt`-function in Matlab for zero-phase filtering, and downsampled to 64 Hz. The EEG and the iEEG data was epoched in 24 subblocks of 120 s for each subject. The EEG was cut into 48 trials of 60 s. The drift in iEEG data caused a signal saturation in each subblock, depending on the individual CI and the radio-frequency link. For this reason, instead of the full 120 s per subblock the iEEG had to be cut in shorter subblocks. For subjects CI1 and CI2 the saturation occurred after 90 s, for CI3 and CI4 the saturation occurred after 15 s and for subject CI5 the saturation occur after 45 s. The parts of the signal that were saturated were discarded, leading to a reduced

amount of valid iEEG data. The valid iEEG data was concatenated for each subject and then divided into trials of 60 s. The number of trials was 36 for subjects CI1 and CI2, 6 for CI3 and CI4 and 18 for CI5 accordingly.

The envelope $[k]$ of the audio signal was calculated as the absolute value of the complex analytic signal that is composed of the signal s as the real part and its Hilbert transformation s_H as the complex part:

$$\mathbf{x}[k] = |s[k] + js_H[k]|, \quad (1)$$

with $k = 0 \dots K - 1$ being the time samples. The audio signal envelope was low-pass filtered below 8 Hz using a 4th order Butterworth low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 8 Hz with the Matlab `filtfilt`-function and downsampled to 64 Hz.

2.6.2. Selective attention decoding: forward model

Linear forward models assume that the EEG represents a convolution of the speech envelope with an impulse response, referred to as temporal response function (TRF). The multivariate TRF (mTRF) toolbox, provided by Crosse *et al* (2016), was used to investigate how the speech envelope is encoded in the brain.

The TRF is represented as the encoder weights of the forward model $\mathbf{W}_{f,n}$. $\mathbf{W}_{f,n}$ was estimated through least squares error minimization between the encoded neural response $\hat{y}_n[k]$ and the recorded neural response $y_n[k]$ at each time sample $k = 0 \dots K - 1$ and for each channel $n = 0 \dots N - 1$. Tikhonov regularization was applied to avoid overfitting, with λ as the regularization parameter:

$$\mathbf{W}_{f,n} = (\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X} + \lambda \mathbf{I})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{y}_n, \quad (2)$$

whereby \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix and \mathbf{X} is a $K \times L$ matrix of lagged speech envelopes. The lag window $l = 0 \dots L - 1$ was used to include temporal context. \mathbf{X}_a contains the attended and \mathbf{X}_u contains the unattended lagged speech envelopes, respectively:

$$\mathbf{X}_a[k] = [\mathbf{x}_a[k] \ \mathbf{x}_a[k-1] \ \dots \ \mathbf{x}_a[k-L+1]], \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{X}_u[k] = [\mathbf{x}_u[k] \ \mathbf{x}_u[k-1] \ \dots \ \mathbf{x}_u[k-L+1]]. \quad (4)$$

2.6.3. Selective attention decoding: backward model

The disadvantage of forward models is that these represent an independent univariate filter for each channel n . In contrast, backward models treat the channels in a multivariate context and are therefore superior regarding the reconstruction performance (Crosse *et al* 2016). The reconstruction of the attended speech stream was accomplished through backward modelling using the mTRF toolbox. We followed the same procedure as previous works (e.g. Mirkovic *et al* 2015, O'Sullivan *et al* 2015, Nogueira

Figure 4. Reconstruction-based architecture that was used to decode selective attention. The envelope of the attended speech stream was reconstructed from the EEG (green) or iEEG (orange) by means of linear backward decoding. The model classified correct and incorrect decisions based on the Pearson correlation coefficient between the reconstructed envelope and the envelopes of the attended (blue) and unattended (red) speech stream, respectively.

et al 2019a, 2019b) in which the envelope of the attended audio signal was reconstructed with a linear spatio-temporal filter, also named decoder. The envelope of the attended speech signal $x_a[k]$ was reconstructed as follows:

$$\hat{x}_a[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} w_{n,l} y_n[k + \Delta + l], \quad (5)$$

whereby \hat{x}_a is the envelope reconstruction, $w_{n,l}$ is the decoder weight for each electrode and sample and y_n is the recorded neural response at each electrode. A lag Δ between the envelope and the neural response was introduced to model the response latency of the auditory pathway.

The decoder weights of the backward model, $w_{n,l}$ or \mathbf{W}_b in vector notation, were estimated through least squares error minimization between the reconstruction $\hat{x}_a[k]$ and the original attended speech envelope $x_a[k]$ using Tikhonov regularization:

$$\mathbf{W}_b = (\mathbf{Y}^T \mathbf{Y} + \lambda \mathbf{I})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{Y}^T \mathbf{x}_a, \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}_n[k] &= [y_n[k + \Delta] \ y_n[k + \Delta + 1] \ \dots \ y_n[k + \Delta + L - 1]]. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

whereby \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix and \mathbf{Y} is a $K \times NL$ matrix of lagged neural responses. For a single-channel signal \mathbf{Y}_n is defined in equation (7), while for a multi-channel signal each column of \mathbf{Y} is replaced by N columns (see Crosse et al (2016) for details):

The reconstructed signals \hat{x}_a were classified into correct and incorrect trials based on the Pearson correlation coefficient ρ . If ρ_a between \hat{x}_a and x_a was higher than ρ_u between \hat{x}_a and the envelope of the unattended speech signal x_u a trial was defined as correct. The decoding accuracy was defined as the percentage of correctly classified trials. The full reconstruction and decision process is shown in figure 4.

\mathbf{W}_f and \mathbf{W}_b were determined in a training process with 60 s trials (3840 samples). The regularization parameter λ that resulted in highest decoding accuracies was empirically determined. The TRF \mathbf{W}_f was evaluated for a lag window of $L = 33$, including temporal context from 0 to 500 ms pre-stimulus, to investigate the neural response to the stimuli. In contrast, the decoder \mathbf{W}_b was evaluated repeatedly for 33 lag windows, with each having a length of 15.6 ms ($L = 2$), covering a total period from 0 to 480 ms post-stimulus, to investigate the optimal lag Δ of the recorded EEG with respect to the speech envelope.

The decoding accuracy was evaluated using leave-one-out cross-validation. The chance level was determined using a binomial test at 5% significance level (Combrisson and Jerbi 2015). For EEG the chance level was 38.6%–61.4%, corresponding to 24 trials per class. For iEEG the chance level depended on the amount of data that was available for each subject: CI1 and CI2 (18 trials per class: 37.0%–63.0%), CI3 and CI4 (three trials per class: 24.0%–76.0%) and CI5 (nine trials per class: 32.5%–67.5%).

Figure 5. CAEPs for all CI users (CI1–CI5) measured with scalp EEG (green lines) where (a) is the vertex Cz electrode re-referenced against the mastoid, and (b) is the ‘CI-like’ condition with CP5 or CP6 re-referenced against the mastoid. (c) is the iEEG (case—E0; orange lines). The CAEPs were measured as a response to ‘loud but comfortable’ (solid lines) and to ‘soft’ stimuli (dashed lines). Significant peaks were marked and additionally labeled when they were in the range of typical N1 or P2 peaks.

3. Results

3.1. Cortical auditory evoked potentials (CAEPs)

The CAEPs for all CI users are shown in figure 5. Peaks that were significantly above baseline level were identified using bootstrapping with 200 replications. Significant peaks were labeled as N1 (80–150 ms) and P2 (150–250 ms), according to their latency with respect to the stimulus. The characteristic morphology of the peaks was most clear in the scalp EEG, using the vertex electrode Cz, re-referenced to the mastoid contralateral to the stimulus. Significant N1 and P2 in EEG were detected for subjects CI2, CI4 and CI5. For subject CI1 only a significant N1 was detected and for subject CI3 no significant peaks were detected at all. Peaks were consistent across the two stimulus levels, with the exception of subject CI5. In the ‘CI-like’ scalp EEG condition, significant N1 and P2 peaks were detected for subjects CI2 and CI4. For the other three subjects the N1-P2 morphology was visible but did not result in statistically significant peaks.

The N1 and P2 responses recorded with iEEG had smaller amplitudes than the responses recorded with EEG. As in the ‘CI-like’ condition, in iEEG significant N1 and P2 peaks were detected for subjects CI2 and CI4. For subject CI5 only a significant N1 was detected and for subjects CI1 and CI3 no significant N1 or P2 peaks were detected at all. Peaks were consistent across the two stimulus levels for subject CI2 and CI5, while for subject CI4 the significant peaks could only be observed for the ‘loud but comfortable’ stimulation level. The latencies of the N1 peaks were slightly

higher in the iEEG and ‘CI-like’ electrode montage (132 and 113 ms, respectively) compared to the typical Cz—mastoid montage (98 ms).

3.2. Selective attention behavioral data

The percentage of correctly answered questions during the breaks of the selective attention experiment was calculated for every subject. A chance level of 16.8%–33.2% was determined using a binomial test at 5% significance level (Combrisson and Jerbi 2015). All subjects performed above chance level (mean = 77%, $\sigma = 19\%$). On average, NH listeners and CI users obtained 87% and 66% correct responses, respectively. Even though all results were above chance level, subjects CI1 and CI4 performed notably worse than the other subjects with 42% and 40% correct responses, respectively. The best CI subject was CI2 with 85% correct responses. The worst performing NH subject were NH3 and NH4 with 83% correct responses. The best performing NH subject was NH2 with 94% correct responses.

The difficulty of the task was rated with an average score of 2.2 ($\sigma = 0.5$), which was equivalent to ‘rather easy’. The story narrated by a female voice was reported to be easier (mean score = 1.9) than the story narrated by a male voice (mean score = 2.5). On average, NH listeners rated the difficulty of the task to be lower (mean score = 2.0) than CI users (mean score = 2.5). The highest difficulty ratings reported by CI subjects were reported by CI1 and CI4 (mean score = 3.0) and the lowest by CI3 (mean score = 1.6). The highest difficulty rating reported by NH subjects was reported

by NH2 (mean score = 2.5) and the lowest by NH1 (mean score = 1.5).

3.3. Selective attention temporal response function (TRF)

The TRF is an indicator of how well the acoustic speech envelope is encoded in the neural data (Haufe *et al* 2014). The TRF was calculated using the linear forward model for NH listeners and CI users based on scalp EEG (figure 6). The morphology of the TRF weights across lags is very similar to the typical morphology of CAEPs across latencies, even though the TRF morphology highly depends on the acoustic feature that is targeted (e.g. Di Liberto *et al* 2015). The TRF shows a negative peak at around 100 ms and a positive peak at around 200 ms. The TRF that encodes the attended speech envelope presents higher weights than the TRF that encodes the unattended speech envelope. Moreover, the TRF weights present highest values in areas around the vertex.

The TRF based on iEEG was calculated for each CI user individually (figure 7). As for CAEPs, the TRF shows a high inter-subject variability. For subjects CI1 and CI3, the peaks of the attended TRF correspond to the N1-P2 morphology of a typical CAEP. For subjects CI2, CI4 and CI5, the peaks are inverted in amplitude. In addition, later peaks after 200 ms occur in the TRF of all subjects.

3.4. Selective attention backward decoding

3.4.1. Optimization of regularization parameter and lag

The regularization parameter λ and the lag Δ both have a high impact on the decoding performance of the model. The effect of λ and Δ on the multi-channel EEG decoding accuracy can be seen in figure 8. The optimal λ and Δ was evaluated for each subject based

on the selective attention decoding accuracy of the multi-channel EEG. The subject specific λ and Δ were subsequently used for the evaluation of single-channel EEG and iEEG. Δ was evaluated from 0 to 480 ms and λ was evaluated for the values 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, and 100. For some subjects multiple parameter combinations resulted in the same decoding accuracies. In these cases the smallest λ and Δ that resulted in this decoding accuracy were used. The results are summarized in table 3.

3.4.2. Selective attention correlation coefficient using optimized regularization parameter and lag

The parameters λ and Δ (see table 3), that were optimized for each subject on multi-channel EEG, were used for all recording modalities in this analysis. We determined the Pearson correlation coefficient between the envelopes of the attended or the unattended speech and the reconstructed signal. The mean Pearson correlation coefficients ρ for all NH listeners and all CI users are shown in figure 9 and summarized in table 4.

The correlation coefficients for EEG present two distinct peaks at lags $\Delta = 100$ ms and $\Delta = 200$ ms. These lags correspond well to the peak latencies observed in the CAEPs (figure 5) and the TRFs (figure 6). The correlation coefficients for iEEG only presented a single peak at around $\Delta = 200$ ms. Moreover, the mean attended correlation coefficient for iEEG was higher than the mean unattended correlation coefficient for the unattended speech at most lags.

The statistical analysis showed that the correlation coefficients ρ were not normally distributed, as assessed by the Shapiro–Wilk test ($p < 0.05$). For this reason, the non-parametric Wilcoxon signed rank test

Figure 7. TRFs of CI users (CI1–CI5) recorded through iEEG. The linear forward model was trained with the envelope of the attended speech (blue) or the envelope of the unattended speech (red). The amplitudes of the TRFs for the single-channel iEEG (case—E0) are shown across lag Δ between stimulus and recording.

Figure 8. Mean decoding accuracies across six NH listeners (purple) and five CI users (green) for all scalp EEG channels across lags Δ for different values of the regularization parameter λ . The lag Δ indicates the start of the temporal window with $L = 2$ samples. The colored shaded area denotes the standard deviation across subjects and the grey area denotes the chance level.

Table 3. Lag Δ and regularization parameter λ that resulted in the highest decoding accuracy for multi-channel EEG for each subject.

	NH1	NH2	NH3	NH4	NH5	NH6	CI1	CI2	CI3	CI4	CI5
Δ (ms)	210	60	225	105	150	240	105	90	60	285	150
λ	0.001	1	0.1	0.001	0.001	0.001	1	0.001	0.001	1	0.001

Figure 9. Mean Pearson correlation coefficients for six NH listeners (top) and five CI users (bottom) for multi-channel EEG, single-channel EEG and single-channel iEEG. The lag Δ indicates the start of the temporal window with $L = 2$ samples. In each subplot the blue lines represent the correlation coefficient ρ_a between the reconstructed and the original envelope of the attended speech stream and the red lines represents the correlation coefficient ρ_u between the reconstructed and the original envelope of the unattended speech stream. The solid line denotes the mean correlation coefficients across trials and subjects and the shaded area denotes the standard deviation across subjects. The subject individual regularization parameter λ (see table 3) was used.

was used. This test showed that the correlation for the attended speech stream was significantly higher than for the unattended speech stream in all subjects with multi-channel EEG, in 9 out of 11 subjects with single-channel EEG in a vertex-to-mastoid electrode montage and in 8 out of 11 subjects with single-channel EEG in the ‘CI-like’ electrode montage. With single-channel iEEG the correlation for the attended speech stream was significantly higher than the correlation for the unattended speech stream in three out of five subjects. Details of the statistical analysis are provided in table 4.

3.4.3. Selective attention decoding accuracies using optimized regularization parameter and lag

The parameters λ and Δ (see table 3), that were optimized for each subject on multi-channel EEG, were used for all recording modalities in this analysis. The decoding accuracies show a high inter-subject variability. A comparison of all subjects is shown in figure 10. With multi-channel scalp EEG, NH listeners and CI users reached 94.8% and 94.6% mean decoding accuracies, respectively. All subjects obtained accuracies above chance level. Using single-channel scalp EEG with the vertex-to-mastoid electrode montage the performance dropped to 62.8% and 75.4% for NH listeners and CI users, respectively. Three out of six NH subjects and five out of five CI subjects obtained decoding accuracies above chance level. Using single-channel scalp EEG with the ‘CI-like’ electrode montage the performance was comparable with 65.6% and 68.3% mean decoding accuracies for NH listeners and CI users, respectively.

Five out of six NH subjects and four out of five subjects obtained accuracies above chance level. Using the CI electrodes as sensors, the decoding accuracy was 68.8% in CI users and thus comparable to the ‘CI-like’ condition. For the two subjects with sufficient available trials (CI1 and CI2) the accuracy was above chance level.

3.4.4. Effect of amount of training material on selective attention decoding accuracy

The iEEG saturation effect was a severe problem of this study that led to a data loss in all five CI subjects. We wanted to analyze how this data loss influenced the reliability of the results. For this purpose, it was analyzed how much the amount of available data influenced the selective attention decoding accuracy. As in sections 3.4.2 and 3.4.3, the decoder was trained for each subject with the individually optimized parameters λ and Δ (see table 3). We used subsets of the full dataset which mimicked the data loss due to saturation. The decoder was trained with 5, 11, 17, 23, 29 or 35 min for iEEG and EEG and additionally with 41 or 47 min for EEG and evaluated with a leave-one-out cross-validation on the remaining 1 min of data. The data was averaged across all subjects for EEG and across subject CI1 and CI2 (only subjects with 36 min of iEEG data available) for iEEG. The results are shown in figure 11.

The decoding accuracy for multi-channel EEG decreased steadily with decreasing training data. For 5 min of training data the mean accuracy of 72.7% was below chance level, while for 17 min it was with 84.9% above chance level. The decoding accuracy for

Table 4. Results of the Wilcoxon signed rank test comparing the correlation coefficients ρ for the attended and for the unattended speech stream. Parameter were optimized for each individual subject on multi-channel EEG. CI = cochlear implant; iEEG = implant-based EEG; NH = normal hearing; * = significant results.

	Multi-channel EEG				Single-channel EEG ('CI-like')				Single-channel EEG (Cz—mastoid)				Single-channel iEEG			
	ρ_a	ρ_u	Z	p	ρ_a	ρ_u	Z	p	ρ_a	ρ_u	Z	p	ρ_a	ρ_u	Z	p
NH1	0.073	0.008	-5.949	<0.001*	0.025	0.008	-4.349	<0.001*	0.018	0.001	-2.133	0.033*	—	—	—	—
NH2	0.068	0.019	-6.031	<0.001*	0.018	0.008	-3.815	<0.001*	0.017	0.000	-3.292	0.001*	—	—	—	—
NH3	0.032	0.012	-5.426	<0.001*	0.013	0.001	-2.482	0.013*	0.010	-0.003	-1.918	0.055	—	—	—	—
NH4	0.072	0.000	-5.980	<0.001*	0.006	0.002	-0.236	0.814	0.015	0.003	-1.456	0.145	—	—	—	—
NH5	0.045	0.001	-5.621	<0.001*	0.008	0.002	-1.640	0.101	0.006	-0.003	-2.226	0.026*	—	—	—	—
NH6	0.051	0.009	-5.405	<0.001*	0.028	0.003	-3.497	<0.001*	0.027	0.014	-2.462	0.014*	—	—	—	—
CI1	0.0887	0.045	-4.923	<0.001*	0.025	0.007	-3.077	0.002*	0.032	0.015	-3.026	0.002*	0.006	0.006	-2.404	0.016*
CI2	0.101	0.027	-6.031	<0.001*	0.028	0.008	-3.272	0.001*	0.037	0.015	-3.282	0.001*	0.007	0.007	-2.262	0.024*
CI3	0.073	0.005	-6.031	<0.001*	0.028	-0.003	-4.267	<0.001*	0.040	0.007	-4.821	<0.001*	0.004	-0.015	-2.201	0.028*
CI4	0.044	0.003	-5.077	<0.001*	0.005	0.006	-0.154	0.878	0.020	0.006	-3.282	0.001*	0.024	0.016	-0.734	0.468
CI5	0.109	0.022	-6.031	<0.001*	0.034	0.001	-5.046	<0.001*	0.062	0.015	-5.858	<0.001*	0.005	0.011	-1.285	0.199

single-channel EEG was less affected by the amount of training data. However, it was around chance level for 17 min and below chance level for less training data. The decoding accuracy for iEEG was below chance level for 17 and 5 min of training data. The results indicate that the data loss in subjects CI3 and CI4 and probably also in CI5 have led to less reliable results and therefore the results reported in sections 3.3 and 3.4 need to be interpreted with caution.

4. Discussion

The present study demonstrates the feasibility of recording CAEPs with the CI electrodes in combination with the CI backward telemetry system. Moreover, it demonstrates that selective attention can be decoded from EEG using such a CI-based recording. These findings might pave the way towards the development of closed-loop CIs.

4.1. Cortical auditory evoked potentials (CAEPs)

Using the CI to record cortical potentials is a relatively unexplored field of research because the measurement requires long recording windows in the

range of up to 1 s and most currently available systems are limited to short measurement windows due to hardware restrictions. McLaughlin *et al* (2012) used the CI telemetry system from the company Cochlear Ltd to measure CAEPs through repeated measurements concatenating EEG from time-shifted windows. In contrast to the present study, they used an electrode attached to the implant case of the CI (MP2) in combination with the most basal intracochlear electrode to record AEPs. They found N1 peaks in three CI users participating in the study but did not observe P2 peaks. Consistent with the results presented in the present study, they found that N1 was negative when the MP2 electrode on the implant case was referenced to an intracochlear electrode. The disadvantage of the approach of McLaughlin *et al* (2012) was that they required the concatenation of the time-shifted windows causing extensive measurement time to record CAEPs. Somers *et al* (2021) performed continuous EEG recording via a CI from the company Cochlear Ltd using a percutaneous connector and a high-quality external amplifier. They tested different electrode configurations and found that the best configuration was a hybrid recording in which the

Cz scalp electrode was referenced to an intracochlear electrode. They were also able to record CAEPs using only CI electrodes, even though the morphology was less clear and peaks were not detectable in all subjects. The CAEPs recorded in the present study show very similar morphologies to the CAEPs presented in the studies of McLaughlin *et al* (2012) and Somers *et al* (2021). However, the present experimental setup was not restricted by extensive measurement time and it was based on a clinical transcutaneous implant without requiring an additional external amplifier. One new finding of the current study is that the peak latencies recorded from the 'CI-like' scalp EEG and the iEEG were slightly higher than the latencies recorded from a typical vertex-to-mastoid EEG montage. A possible explanation is that a signal from a slightly different brain region was captured with a CI or 'CI-like' electrode configuration. A limitation of all studies is the small sample size. McLaughlin *et al* (2012) and Somers *et al* (2021) each included three subjects and the present study included five subjects. Further studies with more subjects are required in order to increase the robustness of the results. Moreover, it is necessary to investigate the optimal CI electrode configuration because the electrode position might be a crucial factor for quality of the recording.

4.2. Selective attention decoding

The CI-based recording technology offers the possibility to record continuous cortical responses in an auditory selective attention paradigm. The present study showed that selective attention decoding from scalp EEG is feasible, even if the number of recording electrodes is highly reduced. In three subjects the amount of iEEG data may not been sufficient to get robust results, however for the two subjects for whom there is sufficient data the accuracy was above chance level. Previous selective attention studies in NH listeners (e.g. Mirkovic *et al* 2015, O'Sullivan *et al* 2015) and CI users (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b, Paul *et al* 2020) focused on high-density scalp EEG with multiple recording channels. Mirkovic *et al* (2015) analyzed the impact of reducing the number of electrodes and found that with a minimum of 25 electrodes the selective attention decoding performance in NH listeners remained stable. With five scalp EEG electrodes, they achieved a mean decoding accuracy of 74.1% and with one channel the performance was 65%. Using ear-EEG, which consists of ten electrodes placed around each ear, in NH listeners Mirkovic *et al* (2016) and Nogueira *et al* (2019b) achieved a decoding accuracy of 70% and 60%, respectively. Fiedler *et al* (2017) used one in-ear electrode in combination with one fronto-temporal scalp electrode to demonstrate that selective attention was possible using single-channel EEG. The mean selective attention decoding accuracy was 70% and it was above

chance level for the seven NH listeners that participated in the study. The present study confirms the results from Fiedler *et al* (2017) by showing that selective attention decoding was possible with single-channel scalp EEG. The mean selective attention decoding accuracy of NH listeners and CI users was in the same range as the decoding accuracy observed in previous studies (Mirkovic *et al* 2015, Fiedler *et al* 2017). This result may be explained by the findings of Mirkovic *et al* (2016) indicating that the number of recording channels might contribute less to the overall decoding performance than the electrode positions.

In the present study, a scalp vertex-to-mastoid electrode configuration was used. This configuration is optimal to capture the vertically orientated dipole arising from auditory cortices that mainly contributes to the early N1 and the P2 (e.g. Scherg and Von Cramon 1986, Hine and Debener 2007). Moreover, this vertex-to-mastoid configuration is supported by the location of the maximum weights of the topographic maps of selective attention TRFs (Crosse *et al* 2016), which coincide with the vertex of the head, as also shown in figure 6. However, the vertex-to-mastoid montage was not really representative of the CI electrode configuration. For this reason, we analyzed an additional single-channel montage that was supposed to mimic the positions of the CI electrodes. Both, the vertex-to-mastoid and the 'CI-like' montage showed promising results regarding the selective attention decoding performance. This finding indicates that the drop in decoding accuracy for iEEG was probably caused by the data loss and the hardware limitation rather than the electrode placement. Regarding the iEEG, the fixed implant case and intracochlear electrode positions limited the area and the orientation of the recording. However, the implant case electrode was located superior and lateral to the intracochlear electrodes. Thus, this configuration could capture both the vertically and radially oriented dipoles emanating from the auditory cortex (Scherg and Von Cramon 1986). However, the exact electrode location could be affected by anatomical differences across subjects and differences in their CI implantation procedure. Moreover, the impedances of the CI electrode might be a contributing factor. In a subsequent analysis we found that the impedance of E0 of subject CI5 was relatively high (15.7 k Ω) compared to the impedances of the other subjects (4.3–5.7 k Ω). The high impedance of subject CI5 might explain the worse iEEG results of this subject. Further studies are needed to evaluate the effects of electrode position and impedances to suggest the most appropriate electrode configuration.

Previous selective attention studies with NH listeners (e.g. Mirkovic *et al* 2015, O'Sullivan *et al* 2015) and CI users (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b, Paul *et al* 2020) used a dichotic stimulus presentation in which one speech stream was presented to

one ear and the second speech stream was presented to the contralateral ear. In contrast, the present study presented both speech streams monaurally to the same ear. This configuration may have degraded the selective attention performance of the subjects due to missing spatial separation between the talkers. However, the results of the present study indicate that selective attention decoding was possible in a monaural listening task. The mean decoding accuracy of 94.8% for NH subjects was slightly better than similar studies who reported a decoding accuracy of up to 89% in NH subjects using a linear backward model with a dichotic stimulus presentation (O'Sullivan *et al* 2015). One reason for this comparatively high decoding accuracy could be the optimization of the parameters λ and Δ for each subject on the multi-channel EEG data, which might have led to an overfitting of the multi-channel EEG dataset. However, the single-channel EEG and iEEG have been unseen during the optimization process and are thus less prone to overfitting and more generalizable.

The lower quality of the iEEG compared to the EEG may be explained by the internal electronics of the CI backward telemetry system, including the CI amplifier, the bit depth used by the telemetry system as well as other error sources. The CI amplifier runs on low power and therefore provides lower gain than a conventional EEG amplifier. In addition, the drift in the iEEG data caused signal saturation after a variable period of time between 15 and 90 s. The time at which saturation occurred depends on individual characteristics of the CI user, including the skin thickness which may influence the radio-frequency connection of the backward telemetry system. The minimum possible recording time of 15 s was already longer than the recording times used in previous studies to record CAEPs (McLaughlin *et al* 2012, Somers *et al* 2021). However, the signal saturation caused a severe loss of iEEG data. In three out of the five CI subjects the recorded data was not sufficient to obtain robust and reliable selective attention decoding results. Based on this data, a group level comparison between EEG and iEEG is thus not recommended. In order to obtain more reliable data for selective attention decoding in all subjects, the recording time needs to be further extended or the paradigm needs to be adjusted accordingly in a future study.

One interesting observation of this study is the correspondence between the audiogram, the behavioral results and the selective attention decoding accuracy across CI subjects. In general, the behavioral results indicate that all subjects were able to follow the task. However, we found that CI1 and CI4 had the highest hearing loss and the worst behavioral results in terms of correctly answered questions and subjectively reported difficulty of the task. This indicates that CI1 and CI4 had problems to understand the attended story, even though they were able to follow the correct story. Most interestingly, CI1 and CI4

also obtained the lowest selective attention decoding accuracies among CI users. This relation between the behavioral results and selective attention decoding accuracy is relevant because it points out the potential of selective attention decoding to serve as an objective measure of speech understanding. This observation is supported by the results from Verschueren *et al* (2019) who found that neural envelope tracking is a measure of speech understanding in CI users and Nogueira and Dolhopiatenko (2021) who found a correlation between selective attention decoding performance and behaviorally measured speech understanding scores.

4.3. Other limitations of the current study

In the analysis of CAEPs and selective attention TRFs the responses when stimulated from the right or left ear were averaged. This procedure might have obscured lateralization effects that have been found in other studies (e.g. Horton *et al* 2014, Tune *et al* 2021).

In this study the CI and NH subjects were not matched in age or in their degree of hearing loss because no comparison between the two groups was intended. The impact of age and hearing loss on selective attention decoding was not analyzed in this study and is still poorly understood. Even though some studies (e.g. Decruy *et al* 2019) found an increased neural tracking with age, other did not find any impact of age on selective attention of speech (e.g. Tune *et al* 2021).

4.4. Future outlook and potential applications

The use of CI electrodes in combination with the CI backward telemetry system to record cortical potentials is a promising method with multiple future possibilities. In order to be applicable in the future, stimulation and recording will need to be performed simultaneously. Because of the close proximity between stimulating and recording electrodes, a high contamination by stimulation artifact can be expected. Since common EEG artifact rejection techniques, such as independent component analysis, are not suitable for single-channel recording, new strategies will need to be explored. An example is presented in the study by Somers *et al* (2018) who included small gaps within the stimulation and recorded EEG only in those artifact-free gaps.

The advantage of a CI-based EEG in comparison to a conventional scalp EEG is that no additional hardware is needed and that it is easily applicable in a clinical environment or in daily life. The technology could be used to develop a closed-loop CI with neuro-feedback functionality. Such a closed-loop CI could be used for objective fittings in children or disabled people who cannot provide adequate feedback. It could also be used for long-term monitoring of CI users by continuous recording of AEPs or selective attention decoding. Ultimately, the goal of closed-loop CIs would be to provide assistance in challenging

listening environments, such as cocktail party scenarios. A combination of selective attention decoding algorithms, as presented in the present study, and source separation algorithms for CIs (e.g. Goehring et al 2017, Tahmasebi et al 2020) could improve speech performance of CI users. Recently, Ceolini et al (2020) showed that brain-informed speech separation improves speech separation in the front end of hearing aids. Thus, neuro-steered CIs or hearing aids that adapt sound processing through attention show a high future potential.

5. Conclusions

The present study confirms that it is possible to decode selective attention in NH and hearing impaired listeners in a monaural listening task. The selective attention decoding was possible using multi-channel and also using single-channel high-density scalp EEG, even though the decoding accuracy with single-channel data was lower. Using CI electrodes and a CI backward telemetry system to record electrophysiological signals remains a challenge. In this work, the general feasibility of using CI-based recordings to capture CAEPs and to decode selective attention has been shown, however selective attention decoding with CI-based recordings was lower than with scalp EEG. Despite a high inter-subject variability significant peaks of the CAEPs were observed in two out of five CI users and selective attention could be reliably decoded in the two out of five users with contralateral acoustic hearing through CI-based recordings.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Hanna Dolhopiatenko and Anna Ruhe for their help during the conduction of the experiments. Moreover we thank all participants for their time and patience. We would like to thank Kanthaiha Koka, Chen Chen and colleagues from Advanced Bionics for providing research tools and advice. This work was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy—EXC 2177—Project ID 390895286.

Ethical statement

The study was carried out in accordance with the declaration of Helsinki principles and approved by the ethics committee of the Hannover Medical School (Hanover, Germany). The participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

ORCID iDs

Nina Aldag <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7393-8353>

Thomas Lenarz <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9307-5989>

Waldo Nogueira <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7224-7617>

References

- Acharya A N, Tavora-Vieira D and Rajan G P 2016 Using the implant electrode array to conduct real-time intraoperative hearing monitoring during pediatric cochlear implantation: preliminary experiences *Otol. Neurotol.* **37** e148–53
- Alain C and Arnott S R 2000 Selectively attending to auditory objects *Front. Biosci.* **5** 202–12
- Ball T, Kern M, Mutschler I, Aertsen A and Schulze-Bonhage A 2009 Signal quality of simultaneously recorded invasive and non-invasive EEG *Neuroimage* **46** 708–16
- Bleichner M G, Mirkovic B and Debener S 2016 Identifying auditory attention with ear-EEG: cEEGrid versus high-density cap-EEG comparison *J. Neural Eng.* **13** 66004
- Botros A and Psarros C 2010 Neural response telemetry reconsidered: i. the relevance of ECAP threshold profiles and scaled profiles to cochlear implant fitting *Ear Hear.* **31** 367–79
- Bronkhorst A W 2000 The cocktail party phenomenon: a review of research on speech intelligibility in multiple-talker conditions *Acta Acust. United Acust.* **86** 117–28
- Calloway N H, Fitzpatrick D C, Campbell A P, Iseli C, Pulver S, Buchman C A and Adunka O F 2014 Intracochlear electrocochleography during cochlear implantation *Otol. Neurotol.* **35** 1451–7
- Ceolini E, Hjortkjær J, Wong D D E, O'Sullivan J, Raghavan V S, Herrero J, Mehta A D, Liu S-C and Mesgarani N 2020 Brain-informed speech separation (BISS) for enhancement of target speaker in multitalker speech perception *Neuroimage* **223** 117282
- Cherry E C 1953 Some experiments on the recognition of speech, with one and with two ears *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **25** 975–9
- Christov F, Munder P, Berg L, Bagus H, Lang S and Arweiler-Harbeck D 2016 ECAP analysis in cochlear implant patients as a function of patient's age and electrode-design *Eur. Ann. Otorhinolaryngol. Head Neck Dis.* **133** S1–3
- Combrisson E and Jerbi K 2015 Exceeding chance level by chance: the caveat of theoretical chance levels in brain signal classification and statistical assessment of decoding accuracy *J. Neurosci. Methods* **250** 126–36
- Crosse M J, Di Liberto G M, Bednar A and Lalor E C 2016 The multivariate temporal response function (mTRF) toolbox: a MATLAB toolbox for relating neural signals to continuous stimuli *Front. Hum. Neurosci.* **10** 604
- Decruy L, Vanthornhout J and Francart T 2019 Evidence for enhanced neural tracking of the speech envelope underlying age-related speech-in-noise difficulties *J. Neurophysiol.* **122** 601–15
- Delorme A and Makeig S 2004 EEGLAB: an open source toolbox for analysis of single-trial EEG dynamics including

- independent component analysis *J. Neurosci. Methods* **134** 9–21
- Di Liberto G M, O'Sullivan J A and Lalor E C 2015 Low-frequency cortical entrainment to speech reflects phoneme-level processing *Curr. Biol.* **25** 2457–65
- Ding N and Simon J Z 2014 Cortical entrainment to continuous speech: functional roles and interpretations *Front. Hum. Neurosci.* **8** 311
- Fiedler L, Wöstmann M, Graversen C, Brandmeyer A, Lunner T and Obleser J 2017 Single-channel in-ear-EEG detects the focus of auditory attention to concurrent tone streams and mixed speech *J. Neural Eng.* **14** 036020
- Finke M, Billinger M and Büchner A 2017 Toward automated cochlear implant fitting procedures based on event-related potentials *Ear Hear.* **38** e118–27
- Goehring T, Bolner F, Monaghan J J M, van Dijk B, Zarowski A and Bleack S 2017 Speech enhancement based on neural networks improves speech intelligibility in noise for cochlear implant users *Hear. Res.* **344** 183–94
- Harris M S et al 2017 Real-time intracochlear electrocochleography obtained directly through a cochlear implant *Otol. Neurotol.* **38** e107–13
- Haufe S, Meinecke F, Görden K, Dähne S, Haynes J D, Blankertz B and Bießmann F 2014 On the interpretation of weight vectors of linear models in multivariate neuroimaging *Neuroimage* **87** 96–110
- Hine J and Debener S 2007 Late auditory evoked potentials asymmetry revisited *Clin. Neurophysiol.* **118** 1274–85
- Horton C, Srinivasan R, D'Zmura M and D'Zmura M 2014 Envelope responses in single-trial EEG indicate attended speaker in a 'cocktail party.' *J. Neural Eng.* **11** 46015
- Imsiecke M, Büchner A, Lenarz T and Nogueira W 2020 Psychoacoustic and electrophysiological electric-acoustic interaction effects in cochlear implant users with ipsilateral residual hearing *Hear. Res.* **386** 107873
- Islam M, Rastegarnia A and Yang Z 2016 Methods for artifact detection and removal from scalp EEG: a review *Neurophysiol. Clin./Clin. Neurophysiol.* **46** 287–305
- Kaya E M and Elhilali M 2017 Modelling auditory attention *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* **372** 1714
- Koka K, Saoji A and Litvak L 2017 Electrocochleography in cochlear implant recipients with residual hearing: comparison with audiometric thresholds *Ear Hear.* **38** e161–7
- Krüger B, Büchner A, Lenarz T and Nogueira W 2020 Electric-acoustic interaction measurements in cochlear-implant users with ipsilateral residual hearing using electrocochleography *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **147** 350–63
- Krüger B, Büchner A and Nogueira W 2021 Phantom stimulation for cochlear implant users with residual low-frequency hearing *Ear Hear.* **1–15** Publish Ahead of Print
- Lybarger S F 1944 Method of fitting hearing aids US Pat. Appl. SN, 543, 278
- Mao D, Innes-Brown H, Petoe M A, Wong Y T and McKay C M 2019 Fully objective hearing threshold estimation in cochlear implant users using phase-locking value growth functions *Hear. Res.* **377** 24–33
- Mc Laughlin M, Valdes A L, Reilly R B and Zeng F-G 2013 Cochlear implant artifact attenuation in late auditory evoked potentials: a single channel approach *Hear. Res.* **302** 84–95
- McKay C M, Chandan K, Akhoun I, Siciliano C and Kluk K 2013 Can ECAP measures be used for totally objective programming of cochlear implants? *J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* **14** 879–90
- McKay C M and Smale N 2017 The relation between ECAP measurements and the effect of rate on behavioral thresholds in cochlear implant users *Hear. Res.* **346** 62–70
- McLaughlin M, Lu T, Dimitrijevic A and Zeng F G 2012 Towards a closed-loop cochlear implant system: application of embedded monitoring of peripheral and central neural activity *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* **20** 443–54
- Mens L H M 2007 Advances in cochlear implant telemetry: evoked neural responses, electrical field imaging, and technical integrity *Trends Amplif.* **11** 143–59
- Mesgarani N and Chang E F 2012 Selective cortical representation of attended speaker in multi-talker speech perception *Nature* **485** 233–6
- Mirkovic B, Bleichner M G, De Vos M and Debener S 2016 Target speaker detection with concealed EEG around the ear *Front. Neurosci.* **10** 349
- Mirkovic B, Debener S, Jaeger M and De Vos M 2015 Decoding the attended speech stream with multi-channel EEG: implications for online, daily-life applications *J. Neural Eng.* **12** 46007
- Nogueira W, Cosatti G, Schierholz I, Egger M, Mirkovic B and Büchner A 2019a Toward decoding selective attention from single-trial EEG data in cochlear implant users *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **67** 38–49
- Nogueira W and Dolhopiatenko H 2021 Predicting speech intelligibility from a selective attention decoding paradigm in cochlear implant users (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.09.17.460821>) (Accessed 21 January 2022)
- Nogueira W, Dolhopiatenko H, Schierholz I, Büchner A, Mirkovic B, Bleichner M G and Debener S 2019b Decoding selective attention in normal hearing listeners and bilateral cochlear implant users with concealed ear EEG *Front. Neurosci.* **13** 720
- O'Sullivan J A, Power A J, Mesgarani N, Rajaram S, Foxe J J, Shinn-Cunningham B G, Slaney M, Shamma S A and Lalor E C 2015 Attentional selection in a cocktail party environment can be decoded from single-trial EEG *Cereb. Cortex* **25** 1697–706
- O'Sullivan J, Chen Z, Herrero J, McKhann G M, Sheth S A, Mehta A D and Mesgarani N 2017 Neural decoding of attentional selection in multi-speaker environments without access to clean sources *J. Neural Eng.* **14** 056001
- Paul B T, Uzelac M, Chan E and Dimitrijevic A 2020 Poor early cortical differentiation of speech predicts perceptual difficulties of severely hearing-impaired listeners in multi-talker environments *Sci. Rep.* **10** 1–12
- Scherg M and Von Cramon D 1986 Evoked dipole source potentials of the human auditory cortex *Electroencephalogr. Clin. Neurophysiol. Evoked Potentials* **65** 344–60
- Somers B, Long C J and Francart T 2021 EEG-based diagnostics of the auditory system using cochlear implant electrodes as sensors *Sci. Rep.* **11** 5383
- Somers B, Verschueren E and Francart T 2018 Neural tracking of the speech envelope in cochlear implant users *J. Neural Eng.* **16** 16003
- Tahmasebi S, Gajęcki T and Nogueira W 2020 Design and evaluation of a real-time audio source separation algorithm to remix music for cochlear implant users *Front. Neurosci.* **14** 434
- Tune S, Alavash M, Fiedler L and Obleser J 2021 Neural attentional-filter mechanisms of listening success in middle-aged and older individuals *Nat. Commun.* **12** 1–14
- Verschueren E, Somers B and Francart T 2019 Neural envelope tracking as a measure of speech understanding in cochlear implant users *Hear. Res.* **373** 23–31
- Waldert S 2016 Invasive vs. non-invasive neuronal signals for brain-machine interfaces: will one prevail? *Front. Neurosci.* **10** 295
- Zeng F-G, Rebscher S, Harrison W, Sun X and Feng H 2008 Cochlear implants: system design, integration, and evaluation *IEEE Rev. Biomed. Eng.* **1** 115–42